

MYTHIC HOMECOMING JOURNEY OF ODYSSEUS IN JOHN WILLIAM WATERHOUSE' ART

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Abstract. *This article examines mythological motifs and imagery in the work of the English artist John William Waterhouse. The purpose of this article is to conduct an art historical analysis of the artist's artworks in order to pinpoint the development of his personal style in the context of him using mythological subjects as inspiration. The author examines the artist's creative path throughout his professional career and the process of finding his own distinctive style. John Waterhouse, a graduate of the Royal Academy of Arts (London), specialized in the academic style of painting early in his career, later on joining the Pre-Raphaelite movement. The artist is best known for his paintings featuring images of women, specifically being fond of femme fatale archetype, who in his canvases seem to come to life from the pages of ancient Greek and Arthurian myths. The Odyssey, an epic poem about the adventures of a mythological hero, deriving from the Ancient Greek myths, was a catalyst for many of his paintings, where he paid particular attention to depicting scenes featuring and focusing on women. It is the theme of mythology and folklore that remains the most characteristic aspect of all of John Waterhouse's creative work. By analyzing John Waterhouse's paintings, which all have the plot of the epic in common, the author investigates the distinctiveness in the artist's style regarding the subject matter, composition and symbolism.*

Keywords: *art, painting, John William Waterhouse, Pre-Raphaelite Brotherhood, mythology, the Odyssey.*

*“Sing to me of the man, Muse,
the man of twists and turns...”
Homer. The Odyssey.*

1. Introduction

Myths represent humanity's first attempt to explain various phenomena and events that could not be interpreted logically. Mythological thinking is immanent in all nationalities and ethnic groups as a cultural phenomenon, and myths, in turn, are an integral part of national identity. Mythology reflects the beliefs and worldview of particular people, closely intertwining with the history and cultural code of the nation. Therefore, its connection with art is not surprising, as for centuries, creators have been inspired to create unique works of art by drawing inspiration from mythological stories about ancient gods and heroes [9, 10, 11].

The culture of Ancient Greece, rich in its mythological narratives, heroic legends, and unique archetypes, served as a guiding light for artists of various eras and styles. The English painter John William Waterhouse is an example of an artist who, throughout his prolific career, frequently returned to the subject of myths, the heroes and beautiful maidens of ancient myths and legends.

John William Waterhouse was a distinguished member of the London Academy of Arts, and his contemporaries highly valued the artistic merits of his paintings. In other words, he was one of the few artists to achieve fame and recognition during his lifetime. Unfortunately, after his death, public interest in the artist's legacy began to fade. A revival of public interest in the Pre-Raphaelites's

art occurred in the second half of the 20th century, which, in turn, sparked the art historians' attention to the work of John Waterhouse. The first monograph on the artist, "The Art and Life of J.W. Waterhouse," was published in 1980 by the English historian Anthony Hobson, a specialist in book publishing. The author's words describe the content of this study: "...my intention has been to examine the origins, training, methods and sources of the artist, to survey his life and work in general. to assess his influence and standing, and to produce for the first time a comprehensive catalogue of his paintings and drawings." [1, p. 9] The monograph highlights the author's detailed study of the artist's academic training, his creative path, the evolution of his individual style, and many other biographical facts, which are supported by reliable sources and archival records.

The most comprehensive work on Waterhouse was written by American art historian Peter Trippi in 2002 [12]. The monograph, "J.W. Waterhouse," explores the artist's biography in detail, including his fascination with Italian culture, the influence of his training at the Royal Academy, and his relationships with collectors, dealers, and critics. It also provides a fresh perspective and art-historical analysis of the artist's works, taking into account the historical and cultural context of the era and its influence on the artist's work. The monograph consists of seven chapters, in which the author covers all aspects of John Waterhouse's life and work [12]. Chapter three deserves special attention, as it examines the influence of mythology on the artist's works, many of which reflect Victorian society's interest in all things mythological and mystical. As art historian Christie Holden writes in her review of the book, "Trippi elucidates the importance of the theme of transformation, whether spiritual or physical, in Waterhouse's work [5]. He describes every nuance of classical myths and suggests how they were likely interpreted at the time. During this period, Waterhouse's paintings became more decorative, and Trippi argues that they belong to the Symbolist movement. He again builds his argument by drawing comparisons with paintings by other artists and analyzing contemporary criticism and exhibition strategies" [2].

In 2004, art historians James K. Baker and Katie L. Baker published an essay, "Lamia in the Works of J.W. Waterhouse," which examines the artist's interest in images and characters from Ancient Greek mythology, as well as his interpretation of these images in his paintings [3]. Mentioning the recurring characters in his works, they write: "Waterhouse's more than two hundred paintings were devoted almost exclusively to women from myth and literature, such as Aphrodite, Ariadne, Circe, Mariamne, Mariana, Miranda, Ophelia, Pandora, and Psyche, as well as femme fatales from 'other worlds', such as mermaids, sirens, witches, nymphs, and lamias. The artist painted more pictures of the last two types than of any other." [3]

In his article "The Forgotten Femme Fatale in Victorian Art: Medusan Sorceress in John William Waterhouse's 'The Magic Circle'" art historian Guy Tal examines the painting "The Magic Circle" and notes its significance for the subsequent evolution of the artist's work, as it is here that he first uses the motif of the "femme fatale," which later appears in his depictions of Circe, Medea, and the sirens [4]. The author notes: "By adorning his sorceress with an expressive figurative allusion to Greek mythology and art, Waterhouse not only shared the antiquarian interests of his contemporaries, but also turned to images of Medusa as a synthesis of beauty and horror, common in romantic and Victorian art" [4].

2.Methods and materials

This article studies work of the English painter John William Waterhouse, focusing particularly on the topic of the Odyssey, being a reoccurring theme of his paintings. A qualitative research methodology was applied to explore Waterhouse's mythic world. Authors employed historical method to better comprehend the social and historical context behind the paintings, obtaining data from the secondary sources, relying on the painter's biographical details and cultural influences of the era. The artworks were analyzed employing art historical methods. Formal analysis was used to focus mainly on the historical aspects of the paintings, such as visuals, composition, color, and shape. Iconography, in contrast to this method, was applied to decipher the meanings behind symbols and motifs within the artworks.

The following paintings, all sharing a theme of the Odyssey as the main motif, were analyzed as part of the research:

1. John William Waterhouse, *Circe Offering the cup to Ulysses*, 1891, oil on canvas, Gallery Oldham, Oldham, England.
2. John William Waterhouse, *Ulysses and the Sirens*, 1891, oil on canvas, National Gallery of Victoria, Melbourne, Australia.
3. John William Waterhouse, *Penelope and the Suitors*, 1912, oil on canvas, Aberdeen Art Gallery, Aberdeen, UK.

3. Research

3.1. Early Life and Artistic Formation

John Waterhouse was born in Rome, to William and Isabella Waterhouse. It could be said that the artist's destiny was predetermined even before his birth, as the family was in Rome due to his father's professional work as an artist. Waterhouse was born in 1849, and his exact date of birth, according to Peter Trippi, who has studied the artist's life and work, falls between January 1st and 23th [12]. However, it is known for certain that he was baptised on April 6. It is worth noting that the year of his birth coincides with the year of the Pre-Raphaelite Brotherhood's first exhibition. A childhood spent in sunny, warm Italy left its mark on the artist's worldview and perception. Ancient ruins, stunning nature, and stories of ancient gods made a strong impression on the young Waterhouse, which may have inspired him to return to this atmosphere repeatedly in his future paintings.

The family moved back to London in 1854, where the future artist found himself immersed in an atmosphere of creativity, often spending his free time drawing, visiting museums, and helping out in his father's studio as much as he could. In 1871, John Waterhouse entered the Royal Academy of Arts in London, initially choosing sculpture as his preferred direction. Later, his preferences changed, and he shifted to painting. His early works were classical in their technique and subject matter, and while still a student, Waterhouse exhibited at the Royal Academy, the Dudley Gallery and the Gallery of the Royal Society of British Artists, which undoubtedly speaks to his high creative potential.

3.2. Early Works and Italian Influence

The artist's early works, such as *"Undine"* (1872), *"The Unwelcome Companion: Street Scene in Cairo"* (1873), and *"Pygmalion and the Statue"* (1873) were exhibited at the Gallery of the Royal Society of British Artists. Many of his early works are in private collections, while some are considered lost and their existence is known only from the archives of museums and galleries where they were previously exhibited. This is precisely why extensive analyses of his early paintings are lacking. However, from surviving photographs and even from the titles, it is clear that John Waterhouse's interest in mythological themes went hand in hand with his development as an artist. Waterhouse's early works were not Pre-Raphaelite in style and have often been compared to artists such as Frederic Leighton, Lawrence Alma-Tadema, and George Watts, who, like Waterhouse, frequently used mythological themes from Ancient Greece and Rome in their works. His early works were acclaimed by critics and the public, and all of his paintings exhibited at the Society of British Artists were sold. The artist also successfully exhibited at the Royal Academy in 1874 and continued to do so almost annually, which provided him with financial stability. Such financial stability prompted the artist to return to Italy in order to improve his professional skills. Beginning in 1877, at least until his marriage in 1883, he made a number of trips to Italy and, according to *The Illustrated London News*, "studied in Rome," although the exact nature of his studies is not recorded [5, p. 23]. During his stay in sunny and colorful Italy, the artist created sketches in various media - oil and watercolor, capturing the architecture and landscapes that were later used in creation of a significant portion of his works. Such works as *"Two Little Italian Girls Near a Village"* (1875), *"The Remorse of the Emperor Nero after the Murder of his Mother"* (1878) and *"Offerings"* (1879) are imbued with the atmosphere and delightful architecture of Ancient Rome, which John Waterhouse was able to convey in his works. During this period, Waterhouse also painted *"A Sick*

Child Brought into the Temple of Aesculapius" (1877), depicting a scene of worship for the god of medicine from ancient Greek and Roman mythology.

Unfortunately, little is known about the artist's personal life due to the lack of letters, his reclusive lifestyle, and the absence of children who could provide further insight. It is known that in 1883 he married the artist Esther Kenworthy, whose flower paintings were exhibited at the Royal Academy [12, 2, 3, 4]. After their marriage, the couple moved to a house on Primrose Hill, which was specially equipped as studios for artists and designers.

3.3. Mythology and the Odyssey in Art

The content of the epic poem "The Odyssey" has been reflected in various art forms, including cinema, music, literature, and fine art. Along with the Iliad, the Odyssey, most often attributed to Homer, is the most important literary work of the ancient Greek world. In its modern form, the poem consists of 24 songs recounting the adventures and arduous journey of Odysseus and his fleet. Simultaneously to the main plot, the poem describes the situation on his home island of Ithaca, where his wife Penelope and son Telemachus await the hero's return.

The events described in the poem take place chronologically after the Trojan War, the events of which are recounted in the Iliad. The central theme of the Odyssey, like many works of folklore of the time, is the homecoming. Not all heroes of the Trojan War, shrouded in glory and wealth, were destined to return to their homesteads, thus the story of Odysseus's adventures demonstrates human faith and determination.

The main character of the Odyssey is the mythological hero of the same name – Odysseus, King of Ithaca and a key figure in the Greeks' victory at the Trojan War. The war lasted ten years and claimed the lives of many heroes, but Odysseus's return to his homeland took another ten years, during which time all of his crew members perished. According to the poem's plot, Odysseus's fleet is caught in a storm while attempting to cross the ocean to the shores of Ithaca. Eventually, they arrive in the land of the Lotus Eaters, where, after sampling the local food, some of his companions forget their goal—returning home. This forces Odysseus to continue on his journey without them. Odysseus's ships eventually reach the island of the Cyclopes, where, through his wit and cunning, the hero blinds the Cyclops Polyphemus. This story is perhaps one of the most famous in cultural history, inspiring such paintings as "Odysseus and Polyphemus" (1898) by A. Böcklin, "Odysseus in the Cave of the Cyclops Polyphemus" by K. Hansen (1835), and the fresco "Odysseus Blinding Polyphemus" (1550-51) by P. Tibaldi.

Odysseus recounts his travels at a banquet hosted by Princess Nausicaa on the island of Scheria. He recalls encounters with the cannibalistic Laestrygonian giants, the beautiful sorceress Circe, and the shadow of the prophet Tiresias in the underworld. Odysseus's crew ventures through the waters of the Sirens, luring sailors with their voices, and the whirlpool of the sea monsters Scylla and Charybdis were all told by the hero at the banquet, as a gratitude to the hostess. The death of Odysseus's remaining companions due to disobedience to the hero's orders resulted in the encroachment on the sacred bulls of the Titan Helios. This story is illustrated in such works as P. Tibaldi's fresco "Odysseus's Companions Abducting the Bulls of Helios" (1554-56) and D. Stradanus's drawing "Odysseus and the Bulls of Helios, the Sun God" (1600-05).

The Odyssey's plot also appealed to ancient artists, and scenes and characters from it are often found on ancient Greek vases: "Penelope at Her Loom with Telemachus" (440 BC), "Odysseus and Calypso" (450 BC), and "Circe Enchanting Odysseus's Companions" (450 BC). Artists throughout history have been inspired and interested in the events of the Odyssey, but this interest peaked in the Victorian era, along with the increased public interest in this particular ancient Greek myth. John Waterhouse, an artist interested in mythology in general, also had his own unique vision of the characters and plots of the Odyssey. As mentioned earlier, women were always the primary subjects in his paintings throughout his career and while interpreting the stories from the poem, he remained true to himself, focusing his creative attention on mythic women.

4. Discussion

4.1. Circe Offering the Cup to Odysseus

Waterhouse's painting "Circe Offering the cup to Ulysses" (1891, oil on canvas, 174 × 92 cm) depicts the episode from the poem where the hero and his crew find themselves on the island of the sorceress Circe. Her figure, dressed in blue translucent silk, takes up most of the canvas, prompting the viewer to ask the same question that Odysseus's companion Eurylochus and his men asked as they approached her stone dwelling: "Is she a goddess or a woman?" [5]. According to the poem, Odysseus's fleet landed on the shore of the Aeaëa, where they met the island's mistress, Circe, renowned for her knowledge of potions and herbs. With her magic, she could transform her enemies or those who offended her into animals. This fate falls upon almost all of Odysseus's men, whom Circe transforms into boars while exploring the island. Odysseus, cunning and armed with his quick wit, manages to convince the sorceress to restore his men to their human form. The painting's protagonist is Circe—a mythological figure, a witch, a goddess, and, in some interpretations, a nymph. Her pose conveys confidence in her superiority, emphasized by the position of her head—it is slightly tilted back, and her chin is raised. Circe is dressed in a translucent blue robe—a peplos—and her dark curls contrast with her fair skin. In the work, the artist deliberately places her above the horizontal line, on a pedestal where she sits on a bronze throne with armrests shaped like roaring lions—animals classically associated with Circe. She holds a cup of wine in her right hand, which is most definitely laced with a potion, a magic wand in her other, and her expectant and confident gaze is directed at Odysseus, whom the viewer sees reflected in the mirror behind her.

On the floor around her pedestal, decorated with mosaic rings, dried herbs are scattered and a toad can be seen among the pile. All of them symbolize magic and hints to the viewer that this is not just any woman. At her feet, on the right side, a black-furred boar can be seen, and on the left, behind her throne, another boar is depicted. In the mirror's reflection, in the very lower left corner, is the image of another animal. These images are no coincidence—they are Odysseus' companions, for whose lives he came to bargain with the Goddess.

Behind Circe is a mirror, reflecting the scene before her. This solution visually deepens the space of the painting, and despite the intimacy of the subject matter, the viewer is filled with a sense of personal presence and participation in the scene. The artist uses this compositional technique repeatedly, and a similar mirror placement can be seen in works such as "The Lady of Shalott" (1894), "Destiny" (1900), and "I Am Half Sick with Shadows" (1916). The mirror's reflection reveals numerous details—a clear sky, ancient columns, a ship stationed ashore, and, finally, the Odysseus himself. Appearing before her, the hero appears hesitant; he approaches her cautiously, looking directly at the sorceress. Yet, with his right hand, he grips the hilt of his sword, ready to use it at any moment. According to the poem's plot, Odysseus, having overcome Circe's spell with the help of a special plant, defeats her with his blade. In later literary traditions, the goddess herself assists him, showing him the way home.

Currently housed in the Oldham Gallery (UK), the painting is one of the most famous depictions of Circe in art. John Waterhouse explored her image in other works, including "Circe Invidiosa" (1892) and "Sorceress" (1911-1915).

4.2. Ulysses and the Sirens

In the poem, Circe, pointing the way to Ithaca, warns Odysseus about the waters inhabited by the treacherous Sirens. The goddess instructs him on how to avoid falling under the spell of these magical creatures:

*"Race straight past that coast! Soften some beeswax
and stop your shipmates' ears so none can hear,
none of the crew, but if you are bent on hearing,
have them tie you hand and foot in the swift ship,
erect at the mast-block, lashed by ropes to the mast
so you can hear the Sirens' song to your heart's content.
But if you plead, commanding your men to set you free,
then they must lash you faster, rope on rope. <...>" [7, book 12, 18-25].*

It was the episode from poem's Book XII that inspired John Waterhouse to create "Ulysses and the Sirens" (1891, oil on canvas, 100.6 x 202 cm). The painting depicts Odysseus's ship navigating dangerous waters surrounded by high mountain cliffs. A sliver of clear sky can be seen beyond the horizon in the upper left corner of the painting, symbolizing the exit from a bay teeming with sirens. The ship's crew rows tirelessly forward, their ears plugged with beeswax and wrapped in cloth for security. The protagonist, the cunning Odysseus, wishing to hear the sweet songs of the sirens while preserving his life, is tied to the ship's mast by his crew.

Waterhouse depicts him leaning forward, as far as the ropes allow him, indicating that he is under the sirens' spell. The sirens are depicted in quite unconventional way for the time—they are creatures with the bodies of birds and the heads of women. Thought in fact, Waterhouse's artistic interpretation of the sirens most closely matches their descriptions in the poem and depictions in ancient Greek art. A Greek vase, dating to the 5th century, depicts Odysseus's encounter with the sirens and, in all likelihood, inspired both the artist's subject and composition. This is not surprising, given that this vase is housed in the British Museum in London, where the artist himself resided. An important detail: just as in the painting "Circe Offering the Cup to Odysseus," in this work the viewer's attention is focused on the beautiful and simultaneously dangerous female figures, albeit characterized by zoomorphic bodies. Another way to draw the viewer's attention to the flying sirens is through the dynamism of their poses and flapping wings, which undoubtedly imbues depicted subjects with an epic and dramatic quality. The painting is housed in the National Gallery of Victoria in Melbourne, Australia.

4.3. Penelope and the Suitors

Besides the adventures of the cunning Odysseus, the poem reveals a parallel plot—the hero's homeland of Ithaca, where his wife and son await him. This plot is depicted in the artist's painting "Penelope and the Suitors" (1912, oil on canvas, size: 188 × 130 cm). According to the poem, Penelope was Odysseus's faithful wife and, believing in his return even after twenty years, rejected the marriage proposals of numerous persistent suitors. No less cunning than her husband, she promised to choose a suitor the moment she finished weaving a shroud for her father-in-law, which she wove during the day and unraveled at night. It is during the process of hand-weaving the shroud that Penelope is depicted in the painting. Her graceful figure, clad in a bright red, or more accurately, ruby-colored gown, is both the visual and semantic center of the composition. Her pose and the movements of her hands suggest she is intensely focused on her weaving, disregarding the potential suitors behind her. Opposite her, on the left side of the canvas, are two young women, possibly maids, assisting Penelope with her weaving. The protagonist's gaze is thoughtfully lowered to the loom, her thoughts seemingly far removed. The window behind Penelope overlooks the bright blue ocean, where her husband is currently sailing. Painted in the finest traditions of classical Victorian painting and housed in the Aberdeen Art Gallery (Scotland), it is one of John Waterhouse's most iconic works.

5. Conclusion

Myths reflect the beliefs and worldview of a particular group, deeply intertwined with their history and cultural code [89, 10, 11]. Its connection with art is therefore not surprising, as for centuries artists have drawn inspiration from mythological stories of ancient gods and heroes to create unique works of art [1, 2, 12]. John Waterhouse, throughout his long artistic career, frequently turned to mythological motifs and images, developing his own personal style that blends Romantic elements with the aesthetics of the Pre-Raphaelites. One of the many mythological themes the artist repeatedly addressed is Homer's "Odyssey." Even here, the artist remains true to himself, as the protagonists of his paintings are not the cunning Odysseus, but images of women, captivating the viewer with their beauty and quick wit. Aubrey Noakes, in his book "Waterhouse," notes that Waterhouse was one of the most popular artists of the Victorian era [8]. Describing the artist's works, the author writes: "With their captivating compositions, radiant colors, and impressionist technique, these paintings delight in their beauty, yet they are also capable of transporting the viewer to a romantic world of myth and legend." [8]

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IMAGES

1. John William Waterhouse, *Circe Offering the cup to Ulysses*, 1891, oil on canvas, Gallery Oldham, Oldham, England.

John William Waterhouse, *Ulysses and the Sirens*, 1891, oil on canvas, National Gallery of Victoria, Melbourne, Australia.

A 5th-century BC Greek vase with illustrations of Sirens similar to those in *Ulysses and the Sirens*, the British Museum, London, UK.

John William Waterhouse, *Penelope and the Suitors*, 1912, oil on canvas, Aberdeen Art Gallery, Aberdeen, UK.

